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***Mediation in the new era:
An alternative way of resolving conflicts and disputes***

Mediation, as an alternative method of resolving conflicts and disputes, is one of the most used non-contentious methods by which the parties in a conflict/litigation choose to resolve their legal differences, both among themselves and with state institutions. The general and the specific principles of mediation (confidentiality, impartiality, neutrality, the flexibility of this procedure) ensure a favorable climate for the management and settlement of conflicts between the disputing parties. Mediation is a non-contentious and informal procedure; there are no written procedures through which this procedure can be conducted but it does not imply ignoring the rights of the parties involved in a dispute. It gives the parties an opportunity to focus primarily on their immediate and prospective needs and desires. Thus, the degree of satisfaction with the mediation agreement is directly proportional to the degree of satisfying those needs. The conflict is managed by the mediator, an expert in conflict management, a neutral and impartial person who is professionally and legally obliged to respect the confidentiality of both the procedure and the mediation agreement, to manage the conflict through specific conflict-management methods, and guide the parties through an assisted negotiation process to reaching the mediation agreement.

Keywords: mediation, legal rights, conflicts, litigation, alternative dispute resolution.

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**MEDIJACIJA U NOVOJ ERI:
ALTERNATIVNI NAČIN REŠAVANJA SUKOBA I SPOROVA**

Medijacija, kao alternativni metod rešavanja sukoba i sporova, jedna je od najčešće korišćenih vanparničnih metoda kojom strane u sukobu ili parnici biraju da reše svoje pravne probleme, kako međusobno tako i sa državnim institucijama. Opšti i specifični principi medijacije (poverljivost, nepristrasnost, neutralnost, fleksibilnost postupka) obezbeđuju povoljnu klimu za upravljanje i rešavanje sukoba između stranaka u sporu. Medijacija je vanparničan i neformalan postupak; ne postoje pisane procedure putem kojih se ovaj postupak može sprovesti, ali to ne podrazumeva ignorisanje prava stranaka u sporu. Medijacija daje priliku strankama da se prvenstveno fokusiraju na svoje neposredne i buduće potrebe i želje. Dakle, stepen zadovoljstva sporazumom o medijaciji je direktno proporcionalan stepenu zadovoljavanja tih potreba. Sukobom upravlja medijator, stručnjak za rešavanje sporova, neutralna i nepristrasna osoba koja je, u skladu sa profesionalnim i pravnim obavezama, dužna da poštuje poverljivost postupka i sporazuma o medijaciji, da upravlja sukobom upotrebom specifičnih metoda za rešavanje sporova, i da kroz proces potpomognutog pregovaranja usmerava stranke u sporu ka postizanju sporazuma o medijaciji.

Ključne reči: medijacija, zakonska prava, sukobi, parnica, alternativno rešavanje sporova.